

Draft Concept and Template: Task 4.2: Just Transformations

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Contents

1. Purpose of this Document	3
2. Quick Read	3
3. Background to Just transformations task.....	3
4. Description of Action & how the task has evolved	4
Original text in DOA for reference only:.....	4
What has changed and why?	5
5. What is just transformations?	6
6. Just transformations and mainstreaming NbS.....	6
7. Research questions	7
8. Focus of T4.2: Just transformations	7
9. Relevant Deliverables.....	8
D4.2: Just transformations: stakeholder engagement process and perceptions for mainstreaming NbS (Sept 2025): Kirsty to lead	8
D4.9: leave no one behind (Aug 2025): Hassan to lead	8
10. Audience for the Just transformations.....	8
11. Research method and Data collection	8
12. Data Analysis & Interpretation.....	16
13. Core Research Team:.....	16
14. Main Milestones for the Task.....	17
Template for D4.2: Just transformations: stakeholder engagement process and perceptions for mainstreaming NbS.....	18
Key Messages:.....	18
Table of Contents	18
Introduction	18
Purpose of Community of Practice :	18
Methodology.....	18
Stakeholder patterns and composition of stakeholders	18
Stakeholder perceptions and views about mainstreaming NbS in MERLIN.....	18
What have we learnt about the application of justice principles?	18

Conclusion.....	18
Reference	18
Template for D4.9: Leave no one behind	19
Key Messages:.....	19
Table of Contents	19
Introduction	19
Purpose of leaving on one behind	19
Why leave no one behind	19
Methodology.....	19
Stakeholder representation	19
Representation across sectors	19
Representation across administrative scale and territory	19
Process of selecting stakeholders	19
Excluded and less involved stakeholders	19
Stakeholder involvement	19
Roles played by stakeholders	19
Integration of stakeholder views.....	19
Involvement of opposing stakeholders	19
Levels for involving stakeholders	19
Perceptions about distribution of outcomes	19
Stakeholder perceptions about benefits of NbS	19
Stakeholder perceptions about cost of NbS.....	19
Other grievances emerging.....	19
Practical measures taken to address grievances and balance trade-offs.....	19
Challenges and opportunities	20
Discussion.....	20
Conclusion.....	20
References for the concept note.....	21

1. Purpose of this Document

The data set out the framework for conducting Task 4.2 (Just Transformations) in MERLIN and how it generates Deliverables 4.2 & 4.9. It highlights the objective of the task, research questions and data collection and analysis.

2. Quick Read

- We have adjusted the concept for T4.2 and its deliverables D4.2 and D4.9 from the original concept in the DoA.
 - T4.2 is 'light touch' to allow time and effort to be put into other deliverables especially the sectoral strategies and cross-sectoral routemaps.
- We will focus on analysis of the stakeholder information being collected across the MERLIN WPs; as involving stakeholders is an essential part of mainstreaming and meeting the Global standard for NbS.
- There are three overarching research questions:
 - What is the composition and pattern of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN sectoral and case study activities?
 - What are stakeholder perceptions and views about mainstreaming NbS in MERLIN?
 - How could considering justice principles (representation, procedure, outcomes) help achieve mainstreaming NbS?
- D4.2 will focus on these questions for the sectors, drawing in the information from the planned work up to June 24 and supplemented by discussions with the sectoral teams.
- D4.9 will focus on these questions for the cases studies drawing in the information from the planned work up to May 25 and supplemented by discussions with the WP or task leads and CS.
- Whilst the task is hosted by WP4 and the analysis is delivered by Hutton, it will draw on the data and expertise from the 'stakeholder coordination' group. These individuals also have time in WP4, to resource the work in data collection and data management. (see section 11, 12 and 13). WWF provide oversight, expert insights and quality assurance on the deliverables.

3. Background to Just transformations task

MERLIN's transformations (WP4) are about identifying "existing and potential governance levers that can change fundamental human environment system structures and processes" to mainstream Nature-based Solutions (see MERLIN workplan). The transformations framework guiding this task stresses that transformations for mainstreaming NbS must occur within the context of social justice (Ibrahim & Carmen, 2022). Attention to justice and equity is an increasingly important aspect of NbS implementation according to recent publications (Cousins, 2021).

A justice framework has three dimensions:

- Representation: are all the relevant interests represented in decision making about NbS?
- Procedure: are the processes of decision making (and implementation, management, monitoring) inclusive, accessible and well organised?

- Distribution: are the outcomes of NbS distributed in an equitable manner?¹

The approach also aligns with the underpinning Aarhus Convention that outlines principles of public (and stakeholder) participation².

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This aligns with IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions (NbS) requiring that NbS implementation is inclusive, transparent and balances trade-off between different stakeholders (IUCN, 2020). The Global Standard also highlights views, concerns and grievances which links to the importance of perceptions and personal world views. This is an important part of the transformations framework.

The IPBES (2019) framework also notes that embracing stakeholder diversity, acknowledging areas of inequality and ways to address them, and enhancing inclusion is a form of leverage for transformations. These principles form the foundation for T4.2 in MERLIN, as these important aspects are not being addressed elsewhere in the WP nor do they have a clear 'home' in the wider project.

4. Description of Action & how the task has evolved

Original text in DOA for reference only:

Task 4.2 Translating MERLIN case study findings for EU Sectors and EU Just Transitions Policy (JHI; WWF Adria, SSGW, WU, ECO, UDE, CONN, UFZ, NIVA, all scientific and implementation partners for 7 cases, sector partners) (Months 4-45)

Task 4.2 will share empirical evidence from WPs 1 (implementation and impacts on Green Deal Objectives), WP2 (potential restoration innovations) and WP 3 (potential restoration upscaling, costs and benefits, and financial options) to be relevant to the focus sector actors that are central to any transformation required to deal with climate change. For example, APE will link outputs from WP3 to Member State's guidelines and regulations for Water Safety Plans. It will convert the cross-case analysis from biophysically defined clusters (WP2-3) to clusters based on common sectoral interests and present the information to national and EU actors at the mid-term and final roundtables. A further reframing of these data will ensure proposed transformations leave "no one behind" by paying attention to the procedural and distributive elements of proposed upscaling and mainstreaming recommendations.

- *The findings from the WP1 indicators and interim results from WP internal upscaling plans and WP3 cost and benefit analyses will be compiled and reanalysed for connections to the focus sectors and enabling peatland restoration and dam removal.*
- *These findings will be shared with the case study boards (via WP1 and WP2) and with the mid-project sectoral and cross-sectoral round tables (Task 4.1).*
- *The findings from the WP1 indicators, interim results from WP2 scalability plans and WP3 cost and benefit analyses will be compiled and reanalysed for their relationship with "Just Transitions"*

¹ Due to the methodology of the CBA approach, we may only be able to discuss perceptions of possible distribution across space and different social groups, rather than offer concrete evidence of distribution of outcomes.

² https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/aarhus_en

objectives; and connection to climate plan objectives. Opportunities to support communities in transition (7, 8, 9, 13) will be prioritised. The data, including those collected in WP1 on implementation processes, will be assessed for procedural justice (adherence to Aarhus principles) and distributive justice (fairness, equality and access).

- *A bespoke regional and climate policy workshop will be held to discuss the lessons for Just Transitions based on the case results (Figure 12). Insights from both the sectoral roundtables and this workshop will help inform the route-maps (Tasks 4.5 and 4.6).*

What has changed and why?

Most importantly, we wish to change the name and the focus of the task from ‘Translating MERLIN case study findings for EU Sectors and EU Just Transitions Policy’ to Just Transformations.

Why? Because we will not be focusing on the energy transition, and this is the main focus of the EU Just Transition Policy. Only a very few of the MERLIN case studies sit within the EU designated ‘Just Transition’ regions and it would require a lot of additional research to connect the MERLIN interventions and demonstrations to the energy transition³. Whilst some of the literature keeps the phrase ‘Just Transitions’ and uses it in the broad manner described above, this could be confusing when working with the EU commission and other EU institutions. We prefer the name transformations to align with the WP title, our conceptual framework and the IPBES transformation approach.

The focus has moved away from the focus on climate mitigation and adaptation. This is partly because we are not sure that there will be sufficient case study data available from our cases in time to present at a regional climate workshop; and the links with the climate & energy plans/adaptation strategies can be made via the sectoral strategies (where appropriate) and in the cross-sectoral routemaps.

The task will be more focussed than ‘translating the case study results’ as we are now using these case study results in many WP4 tasks including T4.1 (communities of practice), T4.4 (value chains), and T4.6 (sectoral strategies and routemaps). WP4 has two complementary perspectives – sectors and territories⁴ – and we will retain these **both** in the task 4.2. We will consider how the territorial approach to just transformations (from the case studies) links to the sectors, and vice versa. However, the focus will be on the issues of stakeholder diversity, inclusion and implications for how costs and benefits of NbS could be distributed.

Finally, this change to the task also arose from the observation that there were over 10 different stakeholder engagement activities across the project but few if any commitments to analyse these data. It seemed an opportunity to use these data to understand how MERLIN activities within WP1-2 (focussed on the 18 case studies); and also activities in WP3, 4 & 5, were assisting with transformations and mainstreaming freshwater NbS. See Figure 1 in section 11 below.

³ This is possible in one or two cases e.g. CS14 and reduction of peat extraction in Finland; or the move to less energy intensive water borne transport in CS10 (both are Just Transition regions) but it is difficult to make a direct link in most other cases.

⁴ the EU, Member States (MS) and regions for selected case studies (2,4, 7, 8, 9, 13, 14, 17).

5. What are just transformations?

The working definition for just transformations are based on two aspects proposed by Cousins (2021):

- Establish platforms for co-production with sectoral and policy actors to help embed new thinking into freshwater NbS implementation to mainstream this approach.
- Enhancing diversity⁵ of actors involved in NbS so that all three aspects of justice are met.

Among other things, just transformations require engagement with diverse stakeholders including citizens, policy makers, scientists and practitioners and situating the transformations within the diverse social, cultural political and economic contexts.

The Green Deal (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2019) has three main outcomes that it is seeking (net zero, green growth, and “no person and no place left behind⁶”). Just transformations are a contribution toward this outcome, by addressing how representation, procedure and distribution of costs and benefits of NbS can help ensure that all of Europe can benefit from working with nature.

(Cousins, 2021) asks ‘Nature-based solutions’ for whom, with whom – and this is an important issue to consider in MERLIN. Our approach builds on the debates in the literature about taking an equity approach in NbS or ecosystem-approaches, particularly Lopes et al. (2021) and Mabon et al. (2022).

6. Just transformations and mainstreaming NbS

Our research on Just transformations will assess how mainstreaming NbS and embedding the ensuing lessons in policy and sectoral practice enhances inclusivity and procedural quality and considers implications for equity. The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Assess stakeholder composition, engagement mechanisms and patterns across different variables (including which type of restoration measures are the focus of the discussion, governance levels and sectors).
2. To understand stakeholder perceptions and views regarding mainstreaming of NbS.
3. Assess how the engagement in MERLIN has enhanced stakeholder representation for inclusion, stakeholder procedures for accessibility, transparency and empowerment; and use engagement to identify the equity implications of potential distribution of costs and benefits while minimising the potential negative impacts on existing stakeholders.

This should be done in consideration of the specific MERLIN context of mainstreaming and scaling (up, out etc⁷) of **freshwater NbS**.

⁵ Diversity to be defined but will include different dimensions depending on what data we have (e.g. gender, age, mandate, ethnicity, geography)

⁶ Recent use of the ‘leave no one behind’ has shifted the focus to international development (European Commission, [June 2023](#)) but the original objective to improve outcomes within Europe remains valid; particularly resource differences between different areas of Europe. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Regional_household_income_statistics

⁷ <https://stapgef.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/Taking%20Nature%20Based%20Solutions%20to%20Scale%202021-01.pdf> or Sarkki, S., Haanpää, O., Heikkinen, H. I., Hiedanpää, J., Kikuchi, K., & Räsänen, A. (2023). Mainstreaming nature-based solutions through five forms of scaling: Case of the Kiiminkijoki River basin, Finland. *Ambio*. doi:10.1007/s13280-023-01942-0

7. Research questions

The overall research question is how does the MERLIN project's approach to engagement of stakeholders in freshwater NbS shape and support just transformations?

1. What are the composition and patterns of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN sectoral and case study activities? The focus of these questions will be:
 - a. Types of stakeholders across administrative scale and sectors. This will help know who were engaged and the reasons why they were engaged. We will also consider who were approached but declined to participate.
 - b. Modes of engagement (how were stakeholders selected, design of interactions, purpose of interactions).
 - c. Changes in stakeholder types and modes of engagement.
 - d. Analysis will consider these patterns by a range of factors and the 8 IUCN NbS criteria as proposed in Ibrahim et al., submitted)⁸.
2. What are stakeholder perceptions and views about mainstreaming NbS in MERLIN?
 - a. Recurring themes and views
 - b. Areas of consensus and differences between stakeholders
 - c. Changes in stakeholder position and views over time.
 - d. Analysis will consider these patterns by a range of factors and the 8 IUCN NbS criteria.
3. How could considering justice principles (representation, procedure, outcomes) help achieve mainstreaming NbS?
 - a. Stakeholder representation (for sectoral, administrative scales and territories). Research questions 1 & 2 by understanding the common types of stakeholders and their changes to understand there is appropriate representation.
 - b. Stakeholder involvement (including roles, conflicts and active involvement & procedural decisions about how they were involved). This will draw on research questions 1 & 2 to assess the kind of stakeholders involved, and levels of involvement, what debates were resolved and whether engagement helped to mainstream NbS. Will also assess whose views are integrated into the process.
 - c. Perceptions regarding distribution of outcomes and the practical measures that could be taken to address grievances and balance trade-offs.
 - d. Challenges and opportunities in taking a 'Just Transformations' approach.

8. Focus of T4.2: Just transformations

The specific focus of this task is **stakeholder engagement processes**, including analysing different sources of information about changes in engaging and working with stakeholders across MERLIN. Therefore, the task **does not** focus on climate change mitigation and adaptation as originally planned. The task will aim to understand stakeholder representation, involvement, and consideration of their views, perceptions and grievances in NbS. These insights will help us understand potential implications for the societal distribution of costs and benefits, to be considered in further projects.

⁸ Contextual 'Variables' to be defined but could include: CS clusters and sectors, geography, project year, types of restoration measures being implemented or discussed. The IUCN are analytical categories. Ibrahim et al, (submitted) "Engaging stakeholders through the lens of the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-Based Solutions: Navigating the Why, When, Who and How "to Environmental Science and Policy (currently under review).

9. Relevant Deliverables

The task on just transformations will lead to two key deliverables, which address the three research questions in different ways:

D4.2: Just transformations: stakeholder engagement process and perceptions for mainstreaming NbS (Sept 2025): Kirsty to lead

This deliverable will be a “Briefing on final perceptions highlighting mechanisms”. It will highlight areas of consensus and differences about NbS implementation amongst national and EU level stakeholders in the Community of Practice (sectoral round tables and other engagement e.g. with the Commission), focussing on what we’ve done, what worked, where perceptions have changed and the reasons for these patterns and dynamics.

D4.9: Leave no one behind (Aug 2025): Hassan to lead

This deliverable will be a “Briefing on mainstreaming restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems whilst leaving no-one behind”. This deliverable will answer research question 3 (How could considering justice principles in mainstreaming NbS help achieve just transformations) while drawing from the results of the **D4.2 (focusing the research questions 1 & 2)** and adding data from the case studies if not used beforehand.

10. Audience for the Just transformations

The audiences for Deliverable 4.2 will be researchers, consultants and funders interested in developing Communities of Practice; and sectoral associations, businesses, policy makers and consultants who might participate in such processes. The deliverable 4.9 should be of relevance to EU and national policy makers and implementers, as well as NGOs, in terms of ensuring that ‘green transitions’ are socially just. In particular, the deliverable will be relevant to DG Regio and potentially DG Agric with the focus on the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (and the recent call for a Rural Strategy by the councils and Parliament).

Both deliverables should be of interest to the MERLIN CoP and is part of good ethical practice to reflect on what has been learnt and work together to consider how to improve.

11. Research method and Data collection

This will be mixed methods with multiple data sources that are qualitative and quantitative.

The data requirements for this task have been identified through the stakeholder strategy⁹ developed to coordinate all the stakeholder activities in MERLIN. A core aspect of the methodology is having real life examples of where MERLIN approaches are contributing to just transformations. Therefore, some of the data are based on experience of at least 9 MERLIN case studies as well as the experience of working across 6 economic sectors. Figure 1 shows the various activities and link with the research questions. Task 4.2 will re-use these data for the research questions.

⁹ Strategy developed by Hassan. Link: <https://nx19846.your-storageshare.de/f/716999>

Figure 1. MERLIN stakeholder activities and responsibilities

Note: For data based on the Case studies, we will use the data as collected and collated e.g. if all 18 cases are assessed in WP1, we will use these data; but where we are doing bespoke analyses for WP4, then we will use the 9 case studies originally identified for WP4.

Note: WP5 will only be about disseminating the outcomes. Hence, we are not intending to use data from WP5 as we plan to focus on the sectors and MERLIN Case studies, rather than the wider audience for dissemination products.

Beyond the existing data already being collected across the MERLIN project, T4.2 may require some additional primary research such as informal interviews with the sectoral and case study leads about the roundtables and other engagement processes.

Table 1. Source of data, responsibilities and deadline

Work package	Data source (stakeholder activity)	Kind of data needed to answer research questions	Due date to provide data	Who will collect the data	Where to deposit data on Next could
WP1	CS Stakeholder mapping	Summary of common stakeholder types, sectors, scale of operation and interests for the 18 case studies	May 24 Mar 25	Pawel & Mateusz, WULS	1.1.1 Stakeholder key findings
	Inclusivity indicator	Summarise number of stakeholders engaged for various stakeholder types. Summarise the common methods ((e.g. workshops, interviews, website, etc) of engagement used. Add you views if any changes are observed for each year.	May 24 Mar 25	Axel & WULS and Laurence NIVA	10InclusivityGovernance general summary
	Full SAT	Generate the overall ratings for all the CS for each Criteria. Focus much on Criteria 5 & 6 to provide to help understand representation, reasons for rating and challenges & opportunities.	May 24 Mar25	Hassan, JHI; Pawel & Mateusz, WULS	2022 IUCN data 2023 IUCN data 2024 IUCN data (to be provided)
	CSBs and ladder action	Provide summaries about who was actually involved focusing on stakeholder types. Also, summarise the levels of stakeholder involvement, approaches and changes overtime.	May 24 Mar 25	Mateusz, WULS	1.1.1 Stakeholder key findings
	Citizen Science	Summarise the type of stakeholders participating their views and perceptions	May 24 Mar 25	Friedrich-Schiller Uni	To be decided
WP2	MiniSAT	Provide the change views about common local stakeholder types and their views across different NbS themes. Help understand the changes in their views.	May 24 Mar 25	Hassan, JHI & Sebastian UDE	2023 MiniSAT key messages 2024 MiniSAT key messages
	RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	Summarise generally stakeholder types involved in the RSPs, their views and any issues about representation. Help understand any changes occurring	May 24	Maria, SYKE & Tom, Deltares	Stakeholder engagement in RSPs
WP3	Financing workflow	Provide summary of the stakeholder types interviewed including their sectors and scale of operation, their views about financial aspect of NbS and highlight any differences and issues of representation.	May 24 Mar 25	Josselin, Ecologic Institute Yulia, Connectology	Financing workflow stakeholders

	Cost-benefit analysis	Highlight the cost and benefits of NbS to stakeholders and any potential trade-off and challenges and opportunities	May 24 May 25	Nicolas Grondard, WUR	CBA stakeholders
WP4	WP4: Stakeholder mapping	Summary of the overall stakeholder types per sector and those actually engaged. Provide summary through notes and reports about their views and perceptions.	June 24	Individual WP4 sector leads by filling in Excel template. Hassan to consolidate.	Hutton/WWF stakeholder folder
	WP4 all-sector questionnaire report	Highlight stakeholder perceptions about NbS and justice issues, their motivation to support NbS implementation.	Now	Hassan, JHI	WP4 sector questionnaire 2022
	WP4: Roundtables and engagement with policy actors	Provide meeting notes, lists of participants (to assess stakeholder types actually engaged, which should be in the excel) and views about various aspects of NbS for each sector.	June 24	Individual WP4 sector leads by filling in Excel template. Hassan to consolidate.	Roundtable: Required sector folder for roundtables Policy actors: Put it in respective COM seminar folder
	CS profiles	Summaries of CS activities to supplement data from WP1-2 e.g. field visit or bilateral notes	April 24 Mar 25	Matthew/Ellie	[Hassan to update when it is uploaded to NextCloud]
	Interviews where needed	Informal interviews with sector teams and/or CS teams to ensure we interpret their situation well	June 24 Mar 25	Kirsty/Hassan with WP sector leads and CS partners	TBC

Table 2: Link between research questions (RQ) and data sources

Research Question	Stakeholder activity providing the data	Specific data	Timeseries	Who will collect the data
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1. What are the patterns and composition of stakeholders engaged in MERLIN sectoral and case study activities?	WP1: CS Stakeholder mapping	9 (18?) stakeholder mapping Excel templates presented by each CS. Help to assess the common stakeholder types initially identified (RQ1a) . Also help address the patterns across different variables such as sectors, interests, etc. (RQ1d)	2021 2022 2023	Individual CS – managed and consolidated by WULS
	WP1: Inclusivity indicator	Counts (quantitative) of stakeholder being involved in excel template. Help assess who has actually been engaged and the reasons (RQ 1a) , qualitative info about methods of involvement (RQ1b) and the changes that occurred over time (RQ1c)	2022 (baseline) 2023	Individual CS – data collected by WULS and NIVA
	WP1: CSBs and ladder action	Information in excel about movement of stakeholders across ladder Action. Help to assess who was actually involved (RQ1a) and assess levels of stakeholder involvement and approaches and modes used (RQ 1b) and assess the changes overtime.	2023 2024	Individual CS – managed and consolidated by WULS
	WP1/2: MiniSAT	Quantitative and qualitative data through questionnaires. Help assess the common stakeholder types actually engaged (RQ1a).	2023 2024	Via CS – managed and consolidate by JHI & UDE
	WP2: RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	Live interactive stakeholder events. Help assess the stakeholder types actually engaged (RQ1a) , and the mode and approaches of engagement (RQ1b) and changes over time (RQ1c)	2023 2024	Individual CS. Consolidated by Deltares and SYKE
	WP3: Financing workflow	Targeted interviews, webinars and workshops where needed. Help assess the stakeholder types actually engaged (RQ1a) , and the pathway of engagement (RQ1c)	2024	Ecologic Institute & Connectology
	WP4: Stakeholder mapping	Stakeholder mapping with updated information in later years. Mainly for the sectoral roundtables but also other meetings e.g. with policy actors. Help assess the stakeholder types targeted and those actually engaged, including who were invited and attended (RQ1a) and changes overtime (RQ1bc) . Stakeholders mostly operate at national, European or international level.	2021 2022 2023 2024	Individual sector leads, collated by JHI and confirmed by WP4 sector leads.

	WP4: Roundtables and other engagements	Meeting plans, meeting notes, participant lists and roundtable or policy meeting reports - Help assess the stakeholder types actually engaged at EU level (RQ1a) ,	2022	JHI & WWF
2. What are stakeholder perceptions and views about mainstreaming NbS in MERLIN?	MiniSAT	Quantitative and qualitative data through questionnaires Help assess the stakeholder perceptions, views and the recurring themes (RQ2a) , areas of consensus and difference (RQ2b) and changes in stakeholder position (RQ2c) at the local level	2023 2024	JHI & UDE
	RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	Live interactive stakeholder events. Help assess the stakeholder perceptions, views and the recurring themes (RQ2a) , areas of consensus and difference (RQ2b) and changes in stakeholder position (RQ2c) especially about scaling up NbS.	2023 2024	Individual CS. Consolidated by Deltares and SYKE
	Financing workflow	Targeted interviews, webinars and workshops where needed. Help assess the stakeholder perceptions, views and the recurring themes specifically about financing (RQ2a) , areas of consensus and difference (RQ2b) and changes in stakeholder position (RQ2c)	2024 2025	Ecologic Institute & Connectology
	WP4 all-sector questionnaire report	A report, containing qualitative and quantitative data about stakeholder perceptions, views and motivation to support NbS implementation. It will help to access RQ2a and RQ2b.	2022	A report already written and will serve as secondary data.
	WP4: Roundtables and other engagements	Meeting plans, meeting notes, participant lists and roundtable or policy meeting reports – Help assess the stakeholder perceptions, views and the recurring themes (RQ2a) , areas of consensus and difference (RQ2b) and changes in stakeholder position (RQ2c) . Views will be based on national, EU and international level.	2022 2023 2024	WP4 sector leads. JHI Collected questionnaire
3. How could considering justice principles help achieve	Full SAT	Quantitative rating using individual CS. Focus much on Criteria 5 & 6. Based on indicators 5.1, 5.3 & 5.5, the data will provide a rating for stakeholder representation (RQ3a) and stakeholder involvement (RQ3b) . Indicators 5.1, 5.2 and 5.4 will provide rating about solutions for their grievance, while indicators 6.1-3 will provide ratings about balancing trade-offs	2021 2023 2024	Individual CS, Consolidated by JHI & WULS

mainstreaming NbS?		(RQ3c) . Further information provided on the IUCN excel template by the CS can help assess the reasons for the ratings and also the opportunities and challenges (RA3d) . This can be compared with years 1, 2 & 3 results to assess the changes.		
	Citizen Science	Interactions with selected case-studies using interviews, workshops and field visits. Help assess stakeholder representation (RQ3a) , involvement and whether there has been empowerment or not (RQ3b)	2024	Individual CS, consolidated by Friedrich-Schiller Uni
	RSP (regional strategic stakeholders)	Live interactive stakeholder events. Based on results in RQ1 & 2, it will assess whether representation (RQ3a) and involvement actually occurred (RQ3c) , and measures taken to address their grievances and balance trade-off (RQ3d) and challenges and opportunities (RQ3d) .	2023 2024	Individual CS. Consolidated by Deltares and SYKE
	Cost-benefit analysis	Targeted interviews and workshops where needed. This will provide information for understanding trade-off (RQ3c) and challenges and opportunities (RQ3d)	2023 2024	Ecologic and Connectology
	Sectoral engagement via RTs	Roundtable. Based on results in RQ1 & 2, it will assess whether representation (RQ3a) and involvement actually occurred (RQ3c) , and measures taken to address their grievances and balance trade-off (RQ3d) and challenges and opportunities (RQ3d) .	2022 2023 2024	WP4 sector leads. JHI Collected questionnaire
	Policy and other actors	Webinar & Questionnaires. Based on results in RQ1 & 2, it will assess whether representation (RQ3a) and involvement actually occurred (RQ3c) , and measures taken to address their grievances and balance trade-off (RQ3d) and challenges and opportunities (RQ3d) .	2022, 2023, 2024	JHI & WWF
	All questions	Overall CS summaries and informal interviews with CS /Sectoral leads	Check of the summaries and the interview transcripts to see if there are any further insights	2022 2023 2024

12. Data Analysis & Interpretation

Many of the data described in table 1 above will have been analysed to the extent that quantitative counts of stakeholder types, patterns and ratings will be available in the ‘consolidated’ data sets. General themes regarding the rationale for engagement, topics discussed, and areas of debate will also be available in these data (e.g. in the RSP or round table reports). However, further analysis to link these data to the RQs will be needed. The sources and timing of these data are found in Table 1 & 2 above.

- Quantitative analysis (descriptive statistics) focusing on the counts of stakeholder types involved and rating for their levels of involvement.
- Qualitative analysis assessing reasons of involvement, levels, views and perceptions as well as representation, and steps to address grievances.
- Graphs, diagrams and images can be used where necessary.
- The task leads in Table 1 should be able to provide the general overview of results for each year focusing on linked the research questions. For example, Hutton will provide the general overview of results based on 2023, 2024 & 2025 inclusive indicator, while Hutton and WUL will provide the general overview 2022, 2023 & 2024 Full SAT. But Deltares and SYKE will provide the general overview 2023 & 2024 RSP (regional strategic stakeholders) results.
- For the case studies, the analysis will draw use all 18 case studies’ data where it is collected but will focus on the WP4 cases studies to draw conclusions and provide any additional interpretations.
- Hutton will then gather all these yearly results for each data and synthesise to address the specific research questions and draft the two deliverables.
- Hutton may ask task leads for clarification if any issues is not clear or if confirmation is needed about some of the findings.

13. Core Research Team:

The following are the individuals involved in the task. The core team (**bold**) will meet regularly, but it may be better to only involve others (e.g. those only involved in specific data collection activities) when required, to save meeting fatigue. The names correspond to the names in Table1 & 2.

The task will be led by Kirsty and Hassan.

Organisation	Individual	Data collection/ coordination	Data analysis	Expert review & comment	Deliverable Writing or quality control
JHI	Kirsty		X		X
	Hassan	X	X		X
	Rebecca	X	X		X
	Leonie	X	X		X
	Esther	X		X	
	Ellie	X			
WWF	Anna			X	X
	Eva			X	
	Geza/Melinda	X		X	
	Fanni	X		X	
WUR	Solen/Sien	X		X	
ICA	Audrey	X		X	

Deltares	Tom	X		X	
APE	Marine	X		X	
WULS	Pawel, Matesuez	X		X	
	Axel	X		X	
NIVA	Laurence	X		X	
Friedrich- Schiller Uni	Julia Vongoenner, Aletta Bonn	X		X	
UDE	Sebastian	X		X	X
SYKE	Maria	X		X	
Ecologic	Joss	X		X	
Connectology	Julia	X		X	

14. Main Milestones for the Task

- Some data will be collated and presented at the AP meeting (Feb 24)
- We aim to have a first analysis of existing data by March/April 24
- All data for D4.2 must be collected and shared by end of June 24
 - We prefer earlier but some RTs will not be held until start of June.
- Draft D4.2 for comment in July 24
- Draft D4.2 finalised in August 24
- D4.2 submitted September 24
- Decide on regional workshop by October 24 and hold by Feb 25
- Data collected for D4.9 (ongoing but by end March 25)
- Draft D4.9 by end May 25
- D4.9 for comment by June 25
- D4.9 finalised end of July 25
- D4.9 submitted August 25

Template for D4.2: Just transformations: stakeholder engagement process and perceptions for mainstreaming NbS

This will focus on what we've learnt working within WP4 with the sectors; and with CS when they have been involved in the sectoral strategies and/or roundtables.

Key Messages:

Table of Contents

Introduction

Purpose of Community of Practice :

This should explain what we mean by just transformations and how the CoP mechanism contributes to that.

Methodology

Should be positioned within the overall T4.2 concept as highlighted above. Also explain the research questions and the corresponding data used.

Stakeholder patterns and composition of stakeholders

Common types of stakeholders across administrative scale and sectors.

This will help know who were engaged and the reasons why they were engaged.

Modes and approaches to changes

Analysing this will help understand the areas of consensus and differences among different stakeholders.

Changes in stakeholder types and modes of engagement

Stakeholder perceptions and views about mainstreaming NbS in MERLIN

Recurring themes and views

Areas of consensus and differences

Changes in stakeholder position and views over time.

Here we will consider what worked and what did not work and the reasons.

What have we learnt about the application of justice principles?

Who was represented? How inclusive were we?

Did our processes help to build consensus and handle differences?

What were the main challenges and enablers for mainstreaming NbS?

Conclusion

Reference

Template for D4.9: Leave no one behind

This will focus on the material from the case studies and take a territorial perspective.

Key Messages:

Table of Contents

Introduction

Purpose of leaving no one behind

Why leave no one behind

Methodology

Stakeholder representation

(for sectoral and administrative scale). This will draw from research questions 1 & 2 by understand the common types of stakeholders and their changes to understand there is a fair representation.

Representation across sectors

Representation across administrative scale and territory

Process of selecting stakeholders

Excluded and less involved stakeholders

Stakeholder involvement

(including roles and opposing stakeholders). This will draw on research questions 1 & 2 to assess the kind of stakeholders involved, and levels of involvement and approach used. This help to understand whether inclusivity actually occurred lead to empowerment.

Roles played by stakeholders

Integration of stakeholder views

Involvement of opposing stakeholders

Levels for involving stakeholders

Perceptions about distribution of outcomes

Stakeholder perceptions about benefits of NbS

Stakeholder perceptions about cost of NbS

Other grievances emerging

Practical measures taken to address grievances and balance trade-offs.

This should stress some of the views already identified in RQ1&2 for D4.2 and issues emerging, and how such issues were addressed. There the issues were not addressed, provide reasons. Thus, we should understand what worked and what did not work.

Challenges and opportunities

This should help have empirical lessons about challenges and opportunities in making transformations just.

Discussion

Conclusion

References for the concept note

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